

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

Deliverable: D4.9 Space Thematic Services Assessment Report

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D4.9 Space Thematic Services Assessment Report

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NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

This document is a final overall report on the assessment and evaluation of the NEANIAS SPACE services mainly from user perspective but also including their technical assessment. Assessment and evaluations processes have been performed for each of the SPACE services release cycles (from release #1 to the latest release #3) involving users both internal to the NEANIAS consortium but also external to the consortium mainly belonging to academic and research institutes. Also, user feedbacks have been collected and, finally, a technical assessment has been performed thanks to template checklists made available by WP7.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

The NEANIAS WP4 “Space Research Services” is focused on the co-design of three innovative set of services in the Space environment for user-communities for Research and Development (R&D). The space services deliver a springboard of tools to enrich the workflows of a wide range of targeted users from academic/research institutions to industrial stakeholders, e.g., aerospace engineering and related technology companies, but also national space agencies and public outreach bodies, e.g., space museums and planetariums.

The first set of services, S1, named “SPACE-VIS”, provide required functionalities that enable efficient and scalable visual discovery, exposed through advanced interaction paradigms, such as the visual analytic, also exploiting virtual reality. Services belonging to S1 have been developed in Task T4.2 “S1 - FAIR Data Management and visualization for complex data and metadata service implementation” starting from TRL6 software modules such as the ViaLactea framework, Astra Data Navigator and the ADAM platform.

The second set of services, S2, named “SPACE-MOS” deliver multi-dimensional space maps through novel mosaicking techniques (i.e., stitching of multidimensional images/maps with overlapping fields of view) to a variety of prospective users/customers (e.g., mining & robotic engineers, mobile telecommunications, space scientists). Services belonging to S2 have been developed in Task T4.3 “S2 - Map making and mosaicking for multidimensional images service implementation” starting from TRL6 software modules such as Montage, ISIS3, ASP and the ADAM Data Processing System.

Finally, the S3 services, named “SPACE-ML”, deliver structure detection capabilities addressing the researchers needs to identify and classify, in an efficient way, specific structures of interest. Services belonging to S3 have been developed in Task T4.4 “S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques service implementation” starting from TRL6 software modules such as CAESAR, CUTEX, VLFF and well-known machine learning and deep learning algorithms and methods.

Services and software development plan as well as the validation strategy have been guided by Task 4.1 “Space sector user requirements, service co-design and gap analysis” and outcomes of Deliverables D4.1 [1] and D4.2[13]. The Space Services now reached release #3 and a most mature stage TRL8. All the testing and quality assessment has been crucial in reaching this maturity and has been performed within task T4.5 “Space sector testing & assessment”.

1.2 Content and rationale

This deliverable, D4.9, is a report containing the details of the testing and assessment processes performed on the Space Research Services for each of the release cycle from release #1 to the latest release #3.

The service assessment has been performed thanks to assessment rounds involving users both internal to the NEANIAS consortium but also external to the consortium mainly belonging to academic and research institutes. Also, user feedback has been collected and, finally, a

technical assessment has been performed for each of the space services releases thanks to template checklists made available by WP7.

1.3 Structure of the document

The document is organized as follows. In Chapter 2 we describe the assessment process and methodology adapted to gain the user assessment, the user feedbacks, and the technical assessment for all the services during all the services development process of the NEANIAS release cycles. In Chapter 3 we detail the use cases assessed for each of the Space services delivered within the NEANIAS Space. Chapter 4 reports the results of the assessment process, user feedback and technical assessment. Finally, in Chapter 5 we conclude this report with a summary of achievements, discussing major issues discovered and outlining future steps to accomplish service final assessment.

2. Assessment Process Overview

2.1 User Assessment Methodology

The user assessment and validation has been performed through the definition of a list of Use Cases with a series of defined steps. The lists have been provided by means of forms (Word forms for release #1 and Google Forms for release #2 and #3) that have to be filled by the end users.

The definition of each form followed the following template:

- *Service validation title*
- *Project Name* (e.g. NEANIAS SPACE)
- *Module Name* (e.g. SPACE-VIS ViaLactea Service)
- *Release Version* (e.g. v1.4)
- *Dependencies* (e.g. libopengl0)
- *Requirements* (e.g. Internet Access, MacOS or Ubuntu OS)
- *Service Access* (list of links to access the service, documentation and any multimedia demo)
- *Validation Designed by* (name of the person preparing the form)
- *Last update* (date of the last update of the form)

Then a list of use cases was provided to describe a service functionality to be validated, according to the following template:

- *Use case code* (e.g. UC-SPACE-VIS-VL-0010)
- *Description* (use case description)
- *Preconditions* (any needed precondition e.g. own a Microsoft or Google account to authenticate)
- *Steps description* (list of steps required to validate the use case)
- *Steps expected result* (list of expected results for each aforementioned step, reply is OK or ERROR)
- *Notes on Use Case* (free text form to add any additional note or feedback regarding the use case)

Finally, the form presents a free text space to send for any feedback on the overall usage of the service.

2.2 User Feedback Form

Additional feedback from users was collected thanks to a user feedback form, provided by each service and collecting the following information:

- *Domain level of expertise*
- *UI Experience*

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- *Result Evaluation*
- *Performance Evaluation*
- *Willingness to recommend the service*

2.3 User Assessment rounds

User assessment rounds to collect information regarding services validation and assessment together by any feedback from the user point of view have been performed for each service release and one additional assessment has been performed before the mid-term review and included in Release #2.

Space Services Releases	Production date	User assessment round
Space Thematic Services Release #1	31/10/20	From sept to oct 2020
Space Thematic Services Release #2	30/09/21	From jun to sept 2021
Space Thematic Services Release #3	30/04/22	From mar to apr 2022

Table 1: User Assessment rounds for each service release.

Additional validation sessions have been linked to the webinars¹ organized for each of the services and reported in the following table.

SPACE Service	Webinar Title	Date
S1 ADN	<i>NEANIAS SPACE AstraDataNavigator: Explore our galaxy in virtual reality</i>	April 27th 2022, 10:00 CEST
S3 LSE	<i>NEANIAS SPACE Latent Space Explorer: Unsupervised Data Pattern Discovery on the Cloud</i>	June 7th 2022, 14:30 CEST
S1 + S2 ViaLactea	<i>NEANIAS SPACE ViaLactea: Exploring our galaxy with a multi wavelength approach and visual analytic</i>	June 8th 2022, 15:00 CEST
S3 CAESAR & ASTRO-ML	NEANIAS SPACE CAESAR & AstroML: astronomical source extraction, characterization and classification in the SKA era	June 15th 2022, 15:00 CEST
S1 + S2 ADAM-SPACE	<i>NEANIAS SPACE ADAM-Explorer: Accessing science-ready Mars surface images</i>	June 27th 2022, 15:00 CEST

Table 2: Series of webinars organized by WP4 NEANIAS Space where user feedback and service assessment was collected.

¹ <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/674-neanias-space-webinar-series>

Finally, useful feedback was gained during the hackathon “Hack the Science 2022”² organized remotely from the 5th May 2022 to the 25th June 2022.

2.4 Technical Assessment

Service technical assessment has been performed thanks to discussion and templates furnished by WP7. Covered areas are related to **service development** (including software development, testing, security aspects, data handling and integration to core services) and **service operation** (including Documentation, Ticketing, Helpdesk, Monitoring, Deployment, Security, Licensing and Service Level Agreement). A list of questions for each assessment area and aspects have been defined as a checklist to be filled by service providers and are presented in the following:

Development

Software Development

- Is the software designed and implemented using a SOA?
- Is a version control system used?
- Source code branch management defined and applied?
- VM/docker images available (if needed)?
- Is any static program analysis tool applied?

Testing

- Is Continuous Integration methodology applied?
- Is Continuous Deployment methodology applied?
- Is unit testing applied?
- Is integration testing applied?
- Have the integration tests been made available in the NEANIAS CI pipelines? Are the Test Scenarios / Use Cases / Acceptance Criteria documented?
- Is acceptance testing applied?

Security

- Are the security technologies identified?
- Are the user’s roles identified?
- Is the authentication bypass tested (e.g. brute force attack)?
- Are all data validated before processing?
- Is the password stored in a secure manner (e.g., using hash)?
- Is every expected error condition properly handled?

Data handling

- Is data handling implemented according to FAIR principles?
- Is the service facilitating the discovery, usage, publication of relevant research products in the respective catalogue?

Integration to core services

² <https://sites.google.com/unimib.it/hack-the-science-2022/>

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- Is AAI service integration implemented?
- Is Accounting Service integration implemented?
- Is Logging Service integration implemented?
- Integration to underpinning services target latest stable releases of such services?
- Is the service properly registered in the Service Catalogue?

Operation

Documentation, Ticketing, Helpdesk

- Documentation available?
- Is capacity building material available for the service? (internal / external audience, video, webcasts, tutorials, usage examples, ...)
- Registered in ticketing system?
- Ticketing system used to plan and track intra/inter-service activities and assist the Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle?
- Is Helpdesk provided?
- Is HelpDesk monitored and relevant KPIs tracked and reported on?
- All documents include necessary tracking information?
- All processes followed have been properly defined and documented?

Monitoring

- Are one or more monitoring endpoints implemented?
- Are the monitoring endpoints accessible by the NEANIAS monitoring tools?
- Provided metrics are useful to measure the service target KPIs?
- Are there any alerts related to the service in the NEANIAS monitoring tools?
- The service can be correctly accessed and consumed?

Deployment

- Is the service deployable in HA?
- If the service is deployed in HA, is the minimal subset of service components needed to keep the service fully and partially operational known?
- A service backup has been planned, implemented and tested?

Security

- Are all reported vulnerabilities under critical level?
- Is sensitive data treated in secure way?
- Are transmissions secured by using some cryptography mechanisms?
- Is the log saved and rotated?

Licensing and Service Level Agreement

- Is the license permits the use case supported by the service?
- Is the service covered by a Corporate Level SLA?
- Has a service-specific Service Level Agreement/Terms of Use been defined for the service?

3. Space Thematic Services Assessment Use Cases

This chapter reports on the established use cases to assess the SPACE Services from the user perspective. For the sake of completeness, we report here the latest defined use cases for the latest release (i.e. release #3).

3.1 S1 – FAIR Space Data Management and Visualisation (SPACE-VIS)

The S1 SPACE-VIS services are tailored for Space Data Management and Visualization. The services provide an advanced operational solution for data management and visualization of astrophysics and planetary data underpinning FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable) principles and are based on widespread and popular tools like ViaLactea, ADN and ADAM.

S1 SPACE-VIS @ NEANIAS Space Portal: <https://thematic.neanias.eu/SPACE/space-vis.html>

S1 SPACE-VIS Documentation: <https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s1-service/en/latest/>

S1.1 ViaLactea Service

Validation form VLVA: <https://forms.gle/CYbhrHvjHTd5Q6WSA>

Validation form VLW: <https://forms.gle/Xg6ggXKYnWKpgzM49>

In the following table we report the list of use cases defined to validate the ViaLactea service and in particular the functionalities related to the ViaLactea Visual Analytics (VLVA) and the ViaLactea Web (VLW).

Use Case code	Use Case Description
UC-SPACE-VIS-VL-0000	Request access to the service through the NEANIAS Service Management System (SMS).
UC-SPACE-VIS-VLW-0000	
UC-SPACE-VIS-VL-0010	Validate the ViaLactea Visual Analytics
UC-SPACE-VIS-VL-0020	Datacube Visualization in VLVA
UC-SPACE-VIS-VLW-0010	Explore datacube data in the ViaLactea Web
UC-SPACE-VIS-VL-0040	Local session management
UC-SPACE-VIS-VLW-0020	Datacube interactive Visualization in VLW

Table 3: Use Cases related to the S1 ViaLactea Visual Analytics (VLVA) and the ViaLactea Web (VLW).

S1.2 Astra Data Navigator Service

Validation form ADN: <https://forms.gle/N7VRrqkS1BPU36ZC8>

Validation form ADN-VR: <https://forms.gle/zYCWxFPTgGezm3Mt9>

In the following table we report the list of use cases defined to validate the Astra Data Navigation service.

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Use Case code	Use Case Description
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADN-0010	ADN configuration and login
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADN-0020	Check revolution motion
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADN-0030	Check the free movement and warp with the selector
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADN-0040	Check the filter panel

Table 4: Use Cases related to the S1 Astra Data Navigator (ADN) Service

While in the following table we report the list of tasks asked to be performed for the evaluation of the ADN VR module.

Use Case code	Use Case Description
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADN-VR-0010	Move in the represented universe
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADN-VR-0020	Use the search panel and VR Keyboard
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADN-VR-0030	Use Orbit lines and Time controls while in the solar system

Table 5: Use Cases related to the S1 Astra Data Navigator VR module Service

S1.3 ADAM-Explorer Service

Validation form: <https://forms.gle/oY5kuLk6CxmhdhZubA>

In the following table we report the list of use cases defined to validate ADAM-Explorer service.

Use Case code	Use Case Description
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADAM-0010	Service login through NEANIAS AAI
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADAM-0020	Datasets discovery and configuration
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADAM-0030	Search available data products
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADAM-0040	Navigate, select, and preview data product
UC-SPACE-VIS-ADAM-0050	Download data products

Table 6: Use cases related to the S1 Adam-Explorer Service

3.2 S2 – Map Making and Mosaicking (SPACE-MOS)

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The S2 SPACE-MOS services provide functionalities for making high quality images from the raw data captured by instruments (map making) and for assembling those images into custom mosaics (mosaicking).

S2 SPACE-MOS @ NEANIAS Space Portal: <https://thematic.neanias.eu/SPACE/space-mos.html>

S2 SPACE-MOS Documentation: <https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s2-service/en/latest/>

S2.1 Astro Map Merging Service

In the following table we report the list of use cases defined to validate the Astro Map Merging service related to the ViaLactea service and in particular the functionalities related to the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB).

Use Case code	Use Case Description
UC-SPACE-VIS-VL-0030	Query Compact Sources
UC-SPACE-VIS-VL-0050 (optional)	Load local image and interact with the ViaLactea Knowledge Base

Table 7: Use Cases related to the S2 Astro Map Merging service and in particular the functionalities related to the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB).

S2.2 ISIS3/ASP Service

ISIS3/ASP services are part of ADAM Data Processing System running in ADAM-Explorer backend. Images offered by ADAM interfaces, Explorer and the API, are the results of ISIS3/ASP services on behalf of ADAM-DPS. See section S1.3.

S2.3 ADAM-DPS Service

ADAM-DPS is an internal, backend service on the premises of MEEO, responsible for processing raw data products into the final products published to the users through ADAM-Explorer. See section S1.3.

3.3 S3 – Structure Detection with Machine Learning (SPACE-ML)

The S3 SPACE-ML services provide advanced solutions for pattern and structure detection in astronomical survey maps as well as in planetary surface composition, topography and morphometry. The service integrates cutting-edge machine learning algorithms to perform automatic classification of compact and extended sky structures or planetary surfaces.

S3 SPACE-ML @ NEANIAS Space Portal: <https://thematic.neanias.eu/SPACE/space-ml.html>

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S3 SPACE-ML Documentation: <https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s3-service/en/latest/>

S3.1 CAESAR Service

Validation form: <https://forms.gle/KKY9D8EfW7mpQ96UA>

In the following table we report the list of use cases defined to validate the CAESAR service and in particular the functionalities related to the web User Interface.

Use Case code	Use Case Description
UC-SPACE-ML-CAESAR-0010	Login in the platform
UC-SPACE-ML-CAESAR-0020	File upload
UC-SPACE-ML-CAESAR-0030	File download
UC-SPACE-ML-CAESAR-0040	Job submission - default options
UC-SPACE-ML-CAESAR-0050	Job submission - custom options
UC-SPACE-ML-CAESAR-0060	Job preview & retrieval
UC-SPACE-ML-CAESAR-0070	Check dashboard
UC-SPACE-ML-CAESAR-0080	Log out

Table 8: Use Cases related to the S3 CAESAR Service.

S3.2 Machine Learning Service

Validation form: <https://forms.gle/2QJgjtLd6is8zZCV6>

In the following table we report the list of use cases defined to validate the ASTRO-ML service and in particular the functionalities related to the AI-Gateway hosting the service.

Use Case code	Use Case Description
UC-SPACE-ML-ASTROML-0010	AI Gateway Login
UC-SPACE-ML-ASTROML-0020	Run Mask-RCNN model
UC-SPACE-ML-ASTROML-0030	Logout from Astro ML service
UC-SPACE-ML-ASTROML-0040	Run Tiramisu

Table 9: Use Cases related to the S3 Machine Learning Service.

S3.3 Latent Space Explorer Service

Detailed use cases description: https://citegr.sharepoint.com/:b:/r/teams/h2020-neanias/Shared%20Documents/WP04-Space/08_Testing_Assessment/LSE-Validation-Use-Cases.pdf?csf=1&web=1&e=jSWrEO (internal access only)

In the following table we report the list of use cases defined to validate the LSE service and in particular the functionalities related to the web User Interface.

Use Case code	Use Case Description
---------------	----------------------

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UC-SPACE-ML-LSE-0010	Preliminary configuration
UC-SPACE-ML- LSE -0020	Experiment visualization
UC-SPACE-ML- LSE -0030	Latent space interaction: Reduction on MNIST
UC-SPACE-ML- LSE -0040	Latent space interaction: Clustering on MNIST
UC-SPACE-ML- LSE -0050	ML expert usage on MNIST
UC-SPACE-ML- LSE -0060	ML expert usage on CelebA

Table 10: Use Cases related to the S3 Latent Space Explorer Service.

4. Space Services Assessment and User Feedback Results

4.1 Space Services User Assessment

The following table summarizes the information on the validation of the Space Services releases (#1, #2 and #3) and includes: the number of end users validating the service and the evaluation percentage on passed/failed use cases.

Space Services	Release #1		Release #2		Release #3	
	# Users	Evaluation	# Users	Evaluation	# Users	Evaluation
S1 + S2 ViaLactea	10	90% PASSED 10% FAILED	15	97% PASSED 3% FAILED	10	95% PASSED 5% FAILED
S1 ADN	10	100% PASSED	22	95% PASSED 5% FAILED	12	99% PASSED 1% FAILED
S1 + S2 ADAM-Space	10	88% PASSED 12% FAILED	8	97% PASSED 3% FAILED	12	90% PASSED 10% FAILED
S3 CAESAR	10	85% PASSED 15% FAILED	13	95% PASSED 5% FAILED	6	100% PASSED 0% FAILED
S3 AstroML	10	93% PASSED 7% FAILED	7	94% PASSED 6% FAILED	10	100% PASSED 0% FAILED
S3 LSE	N/A		N/A		6	90% PASSED 10% FAILED

Table 11: Number of end users and results of the evaluation on the use cases to assess the NEANIAS SPACE Services releases (release #1, #2 and #3)

All the validation procedures for each service and the results of the validation by end users have been collected by the Google Forms and are stored on the NEANIAS Documentation Repository³ in the WP4 area.

³NEANIAS Documentation Repository: https://citegr.sharepoint.com/:f/r/teams/h2020-neanias/Shared%20Documents/WP04-Space/08_Testing_Assessment/External_Validation_Doc?csf=1&web=1&e=pgVp5e (internal use only)

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Overall feedback from release #1 and release #2 were mainly addressed to the improvement on the UI and the user experience. In particular for the ViaLactea service some difficulties arose from the installation procedure of the desktop client that led to the development of a container to ease the installation procedure and to the development of the web client.

For ADN the UI has been improved, as well as the control and movement system via mouse and keyboard. It has also been enriched in terms of objects, information and functionalities that allow better use of this data.

For ADAM-Explorer, the user interface experience has been improved to include more data products metadata filtering parameters, and landing sites used by past and current Mars exploration rover missions have also been included to help the users interact and access data on Martian “hotspots”, directing users to regions of the planet where data products are more numerous.

For CAESAR, the feedback gathered over the successive releases has contributed to identify bugs, both in the web interface and in the backend, and improve the overall user experience. The architecture design (going from a command line tool to a fully distributed service operating on a k8s cluster) has greatly benefited from having multiple users working simultaneously on the platform, serving as an ad hoc stress test in a real scenario, and allowing us to further optimize scalability and stability. The incremental addition of new features on top of previously validated versions (e.g. the addition of job result previsualization in release #2, or the support for other source finders like AEGEAN and CuTEX in release #3, with many more customization options) has allowed us to quickly spot issues and corner cases not considered during the implementation, and solve them efficiently with minimal impact on the service availability. Finally, the quality of the documentation has been gradually improved, in compliance with the EOSC onboarding requisites.

ASTRO-ML models have been evaluated for testing classification of different radio astronomical sources (compact sources, multicomponent sources and sidelobe artifacts) employing two different ML models (Mask R-CNN and Tiramisu) using the C3 core AI Gateway. Feedback from users led to the integration of the models to the CAESAR service so that users can now perform classification of sources employing the same tool.

Finally, for Latent Space Explorer (LSE) the validation has been performed only for the Release #3 because the service has been included in production within the NEANIAS Space Services at a later stage and the validation has been performed in live sessions conducted by a UX expert. The sessions were recorded and stored internally at UNIMIB, before analysing the produced data. A System Usability Scale⁴ table has been compiled and it is available on the NEANIAS Documentation Repository⁵ in the WP4 area together with the results of all SPACE services user assessment and evaluation rounds.

⁴ See: Brooke, J. (2020). SUS: A “Quick and Dirty” Usability Scale. In *Usability Evaluation In Industry* (pp. 207–212). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781498710411-35>

⁵NEANIAS Documentation Repository: [08 Testing Assessment](#) (internal use only)

4.2 Space Services User Feedback

All the details regarding the received user feedback for all SPACE Services can be found on the NEANIAS Documentation Repository⁶.

ViaLactea User Feedback results

The ViaLactea service actually counts 45 users mainly researchers working at universities or research institutes. It is being used also in other projects such as SKA⁷, being evaluated as one prototype for the regional centers, and the ECOGAL⁸ project for supporting the understanding our Galactic ecosystem in particular for the studies related to the formation sites of stars and planets.

Feedback from users was collected by using the following Google Form: <https://forms.gle/HGsDK5GVko2eD3YH9>

Regarding the experience using the ViaLactea graphical user interface (either by using the VLVA desktop client or VLW web interface) and the quality of the results, the 90% of users found it excellent. While the processing time was found reasonable by the 70% of users. This may depend on the kind of queries made to the VLKB databases.

Users appreciated the video demo to quick start with the service usage. A member from the EAB commented that the service looks similar to Aladin⁹ and suggested to make a comparison of functionality with Aladin when presenting it to the users. This comparison is actually being performed in the framework of the SKA and results will be presented soon. Finally, a comment was related to the load a local large datacubes that should be optimized by exploiting accelerators (e.g. GPUs) or parallel programming paradigms.

ADN User Feedback results

The ADN service counts 30 users between researchers, planetary scientists and students.

Feedback was collected by using Google Form: <https://forms.gle/N7VRrqkS1BPU36ZC8>

Over 90% of test runs were successful.

All users believe that the configuration system is at least good or excellent, while only 90% of users believe the loading time is acceptable.

The graphical interface and the interaction system obtained excellent ratings from all users. Most of the suggestions were received on the configuration system which, however simple it may be, could be transformed into a more user-friendly system.

⁶ [SPACE Services User Feedback reports](#) (internal use only)

⁷ <https://www.skatelescope.org/the-ska-project/>

⁸ <http://www.ecogal.eu/>

⁹ <https://aladin.u-strasbg.fr/>

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The ADN VR counts 11 users from the University of Portsmouth staff and students.

Feedback was collected using Google Form: <https://forms.gle/RyWeK9PnLgQwQ3TGA>

Over 70% of users found the interaction with the menu satisfying or good enough, with 40% of the users finding the UI interaction intuitive.

80% of users found the navigation of the environment within ADN VR comfortable.

Most of the user suggestions focussed on the Interaction with the UI and how to improve it and present a more user-friendly interface.

ADAM-SPACE User Feedback results

ADAM-Space, the Explorer and the API through Space-VIS service, counts with 26 users composed by geologists (80%), physicists (10%), and data science students (10%). Referred by the Europlanet-GMAP project as source for Mars *basemap* images. The platform was used during NEANIAS' Hack the Science 2022 data challenge by two teams on the exploration and access to thousands of Martian images. All of our users are in European territory.

Feedback from the users were taken using validation¹⁰ and feedback¹¹ forms, as well as the Slack¹² channel used during the hackathon. The overall feedback was very positive, the direct access to high-level Martian images was/is a very welcome service recognized by some of the users with expertise in planetary sciences. The explorer interface and its performance were satisfactory, user interface feedback could be improved, such as a preview and estimate of the total download volume of large datasets. For the last release (#3) we improved the Explorer user space to include a set of past and current landing sites as they provide great coverage and are typically of general interest for experts as well as non-experts. During the Hack the Planets challenge we interacted with the participants through the chat platform which allowed us to fix some issues on the ADAM-API. The users were using either NEANIAS Space-VIS (JupyterHub) service or setup on their premises.

CAESAR User Feedback results

The current CAESAR service user base is composed of 34 users, mostly astrophysicists from INAF research institutes. The application of CAESAR in real world scenarios is circumscribed to source extraction and catalogue production in SKA precursor projects, like ASKAPⁱ, and MeerKATⁱⁱ. The integration of CAESAR as one of the cornerstones of the toolset in the upcoming SKA Regional Centers is also foreseen.

¹⁰ ADAM-Space validation form: <https://forms.gle/SSFfHXfwWMcSAmQ5A>

¹¹ ADAM-Space user feedback form: <https://forms.gle/VPs69qzhNjnV4CNC8>

¹² Slack: <https://hack-the-science-2022.slack.com>

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For the initial releases, feedback from end users was collected using a Google Form: <https://forms.gle/99XypDSiG1CS6JuR9>, asking to rate the ease-of-use and utility of several features of the UI. The results were positive, with >90% of the respondents highlighting the usefulness of job previsualization and 70% agreeing that the job submission process is straightforward. Additional feedback was collected during the Hack the Science 2022 hackathon, in which multidisciplinary teams composed of astrophysicists and data scientists were challenged to solve an astrophysics-related problem using the NEANIAS services. In the course of the hackathon, that lasted for a month, we received continuous feedback from the teams, which provided valuable inputs on how to improve the user experience (e.g. clarity of the web interface options, quality and availability of REST API documentation). The overall experience was positive, with the participants being able to successfully extract compact sources in their infrared maps from WISE –which was one of the 1st steps of their task-. In addition, this proved the potential of CAESAR beyond its original domain (radioastronomy).

ASTRO-ML User Feedback results

The ASTRO-ML Service is currently being made available from the CAESAR Service and from the AI Gateway Core Service provided by WP6 C3 services. This section summarizes the user feedback received from using the service from the AI-Gateway (for information on the feedback of CAESAR please refer to the previous section 4.2.4).

The AI Gateway actually counts about 170 users, the service makes available two environments enabling two Deep Learning models, Mask R-CNN and Tiramisu respectively performing object detection and semantic segmentation of radio astronomical maps. The service is foreseen to be used by researchers and students involved in SKA precursors and pathfinders.

Feedback from users was collected by using the following Google Form: <https://forms.gle/PDxJoWUJYptQCJbw5>

80% of respondents had high experience in Machine Learning and Deep Learning and found the graphical user interface (based on Jupyter Hub) good as well as the quality of the results, while the 60% of respondents found time to produce the results reasonable and the 20% found it poor maybe referring to the overload time to spawn the environments.

LSE User Feedback results

LSE has collected feedback from three different types of users: internal users (people involved in the conception, design, and development of the service), test users (people specifically asked to evaluate the service without prior involvement) and hackathon users (participants to a hackathon that evaluated the service for sake of potential usage for their projects). Internal users included domain experts in the space sector, so we collected especially feedback on new useful features to be developed and evaluations on the developed service. The direct contact with the internal users, however, limits the capability to detect issues related either to a poor documentation or on GUI usability. Therefore, live tests on new users were made and

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recorded to grasp useful feedback on UI accessibility. The need of a better we application layout was spotted. Feedback collected was useful to prepare a hackathon ([HACKTHESCIENCE2022](#)), in which we acquired final feedbacks from the teams without detecting any particular issue.

In order to make common statistics between all type of users, a google form (analogous to the one adopted by other services for acquiring user feedback) was submitted to all users: <https://forms.gle/k2ExjpkQ2YsEjSpt8>

Results are summarized below for a total of 18 users from different level of expertise.

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		Domain level of expertise		
		Low	High	Expert
Number of users		6	5	7
UI Experience				
1	Poor	0%	0%	0%
2	Satisfactory	33%	20%	29%
3	Excellent	67%	80%	71%
Result Evaluation				
1	Poor	0%	0%	0%
2	Satisfactory	50%	60%	57%
3	Excellent	50%	40%	43%
Performance Evaluation				
1	Poor	0%	0%	0%
2	Satisfactory	83%	40%	71%
3	Excellent	17%	60%	29%
Willingness to recommend		83%	100%	100%

Table 12: User Feedback results on the evaluation of the Latent Space Explorer (release #3) grouped in three different level of domain expertise.

4.3 Space Services Technical Assessment

In this section we summarize the results regarding the technical assessment as defined in the methodology described in Section 2.4.

The results of the development of the SPACE services are reported in Figure 1. All the software code used to develop the services have been stored following a version control system and the source code branch management has been defined and applied and none of them have employed any static program analysis tool. No Continuous Integration or Continuous Deployment methodology have been applied and no unit testing or integration testing while those are planned. All Test Scenarios / Use Cases / Acceptance Criteria have been however documented and acceptance testing is applied. For almost all services the security technologies have been and the user's roles have been identified. All data are validated before processing except in ASTRO-ML service, and expected error conditions are properly handled. Data handling have been implemented according to FAIR principles for all services and almost all services facilitate the discovery, usage, publication of relevant research products in the respective catalogues.

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Integration to core services (AAI, Accounting and Logging) have been implemented for all services (N/A for accounting and logging in ADN service), and the integration underpin services targeting the latest stable releases. Finally, all the SPACE services have been properly registered in the NEANIAS Service Catalogue.

Figure 1: Results of the Technical assessment on the development areas of the SPACE services.

The results of the operation of the SPACE services are reported in Figure 2. Documentation is available for all SPACE Services and also capacity building material: video demos, webinars, tutorials and usage examples.

All services except ADAM-SPACE and LSE are registered in the NEANIAS ticketing system that is used to plan and track intra/inter-service activities and assist the Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle. Helpdesk is provided for all services but not used for all to be monitored and to track and report relevant KPIs. All documents include necessary tracking information.

Monitoring endpoints are all checked by NEANIAS Monitoring systems (except the desktop client tools), they provided useful metrics to measure the service target KPIs, while no alerts related to the services in the NEANIAS monitoring tools have been implemented. All services except ViaLactea and ADN are deployable in HA and the minimal subset of service components needed to keep the service fully and partially operational are defined in CAESAR and ASTRO-ML. Only ADAM-SPACE provides service backup systems.

For all services all reported vulnerabilities were under a critical level and sensitive data are treated in secure way. Transmissions were secured by using some cryptography mechanisms and the log saved in the Logging system. Finally, the defined licenses permit all the use cases supported by the services. Only ADN service is covered by a Corporate Level SLA and all services, except ASTRO-ML that is however included in CAESAR and AI-Gateway, have defined service-specific Service Level Agreement and Terms of Use.

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Figure 2: Results of the Technical assessment on the Operation areas of the SPACE services.

All the details regarding the technical assessment of all SPACE Services for each NEANIAS release cycle can be found on the NEANIAS Documentation Repository¹³ in the WP4 area.

5. Summary

This document presents a final overview on the assessment and evaluation processes of the NEANIAS SPACE services. It summarizes the main outcomes of a continuous evaluation of the services from a final user perspective, as well as a detailed technical assessment performed according to the templates provided by WP7, focusing on development and operational aspects.

Assessment and evaluations processes have been performed for each of the SPACE services release cycles (from release #1 to the latest release #3) involving users both internal and external to the NEANIAS consortium. The user base covered a wide range of technical backgrounds, with most users belonging to academic and research institutes and having different levels of expertise (from students to senior scientists).

User feedback has been collected thanks to engagement events using different means, mailing lists, webinars, workshops and conferences. This feedback has provided useful insights that have allowed us to progressively improve the services, enhancing availability, stability and user experience until reaching TRL8 and onboarding on EOSC.

¹³ [NEANIAS SPACE Services Assessment reports](#) (internal use only)

References

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- [15] NEANIAS WP4 Collaboration, "D4.7: Space Thematic Services Release #3," NEANIAS, 2022.
- [16] NEANIAS WP4 Collaboration, "D4.8: Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #3) ," NEANIAS, 2022.

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management platform
ADN	Astra Data Navigator
CAESAR	Compact And Extended Source Automated Recognition
CRISM	Compact Reconnaissance Imaging Spectrometer for Mars
DL	Deep Learning
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPN-TAP	EuroPlanet - Table Access Protocol
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FITS	Flexible Image Transport System
IVOA	International Virtual Observatory Alliance
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
MRO	Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OS	Operating System
SKA	Square Kilometer Array
TAP	Table Access Protocol
VLFF	ViaLactea Filament Finder
VLKB	ViaLactea Knowledge Base
VLVA	ViaLactea Visual Analytics
VLW	ViaLactea Web
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Features Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WPS	Web Processing Service

ⁱ Riggi et al. 2020, 10.1093/mnras/stab028

ⁱⁱ Bordiu et al. 2022, in prep.